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A Proactive Approach to the Recovery and Recycling of Photovoltaic Modules

D12.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan (1)

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Terms, definitions, and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement
RP	Report
D	Deliverable
T	Task
WP	Work Package
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

1. Executive summary

The present deliverable D12.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan (1) outlines the comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy plan for the APOLLO project, as part of Task 12.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities under the work package WP12 “Exploitation and Communication (P1) “. This document serves as an internal practical guide for project partners to effectively engage in communication and dissemination activities.

The strategy summarizes the consortium’s approach and specific actions aimed at disseminating and communicating the results generated by the APOLLO project. Its primary objectives include raising public awareness of the project and its results, as well as showcasing the benefits of the new technologies introduced. The strategy plan sets out what dissemination and communication activities have already been achieved and provides an outline of what is planned till the end of the project.

An overview of dissemination and communication opportunities was identified through traditional channels such as event attendance and organization (e.g., conferences, seminars, workshops, fairs, etc.), project publications (e.g., brochures, posters, press releases as well as conference papers, articles in professional journals, etc.) and project presentations, complemented also by online activities as the project website, newsletters, and the main social network profiles.

The dissemination activities were designed to ensure effective communication and engagement with the key audiences, the public (e.g., through low-level infographics), policymakers (e.g., policy briefs, demo materials, etc.), and stakeholders to maximize awareness about the APOLLO project and its results.

1.1 Obligation to disseminate the project results

As stated in the APOLLO Grant Agreement article 17 “COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND VISIBILITY”, unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), following Annex 1 and a strategic, coherent and effective manner.

Before engaging in a communication or dissemination activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the granting authority. As stated in ANNEX 5, the beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules, or legitimate interests.

A beneficiary intending to share its results must notify other beneficiaries at least 15 days in advance, providing enough information about the results. Within 15 days of receiving the notification, other beneficiaries can object if they can demonstrate significant harm to their legitimate interests related to the results or background. In such cases, the results cannot be shared unless measures are taken to protect those interests. If the call conditions require additional sharing obligations, the beneficiaries must also comply with them.

Furthermore, unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, and information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement shown below.

Additionally, any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information and must indicate the disclaimer “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

FIGURE 1 EU EMBLEMS

2. Communication and dissemination strategy

One of the main goals of WP12 is to reach the widest dissemination of the results generated by the APOLLO project and raise public awareness of the project. In this framework, a strong communication strategy was set up to make the most of reaching the target impact. The whole APOLLO consortium is committed to performing dissemination activities and proactively looking for dissemination opportunities.

Communication activities aim at creating a common project visual identity and public image, raising basic interest in the proposed technology and processes, providing up-to-date information about the project, and translating the scientific/technical results into messages that can be read and understood by a wide public. The dissemination and communication strategy addresses the identification of target audiences, goals to be reached for each audience, types of messages, and how and when the communication takes place, as well as the roles and responsibilities of the project partners.

2.1 Target audience and stakeholders

The APOLLO project is currently implementing the impact-driven Communication and Dissemination strategy aimed at effectively engaging various target audiences and stakeholders, which include:

TABLE 1 TARGET AUDIENCES AND STAKEHOLDERS

Target Group	Example(s)
TG1: Research & Scientific Community	Universities, Research Organisations, Applied research centres
TG2: End Users	Commercial recyclers, associations, trade organisations
TG3: Financial Actors	Institutional Investors, company shareholders
TG4: Innovators, Designers	PV panel designers, PV production equipment designers, PV recycling line equipment designers
TG5: Suppliers (Equipment, Materials)	PV recycling and production equipment providers, Consumables providers (solvents, materials for recycling process), PV material refiners and suppliers
TG6: PV Manufacturers	Wafer manufacturers, cell manufacturers, module and panel manufacturers
TG7: Policy makers, Associations and Alliances	Local/Regional/National authorities, Regulatory bodies, Policy advisors, international organizations, EU institutions, European Solar PV Industry Alliance
TG8: General Public	Local stakeholders, civil society, citizens
TG9: External Industrial Advisors	Reiling Recycling Group, others to be confirmed during the project.
TG10: Waste collectors, traders	Local/Regional/National authorities, recyclers, middlemen, PV manufacturers

2.2 Key messages

The APOLLO project aims to effectively communicate and disseminate key messages about the technologies developed within the project, adhering to clear communication principles that engage the targeted audience and stakeholders. Key Messages that will be targeted are:

- a) process performance results,
- b) techno-economic process data,
- c) process environmental performance,
- d) investment required/capex
- e) PV design guidelines for improved recyclability,
- f) Process optimization info,
- g) Equipment optimization info,
- h) Training materials
- i) Standards validations
- j) Policy recommendations
- k) DPP and marketplace information

2.3 Tools

Dissemination activities will be targeted both nationally and internationally. The tools that are and will be used for dissemination are the following:

- Publications (scientific, technical, and economic journals, popular magazines, and newspapers).
- Events (conferences, congresses, workshops, seminars, forums participation, fairs, exhibitions participation, public workshops, webinars organization).
- Press releases (media articles).
- Digital media (project website, social media profiles, thematic portals, media outlets, and online ads will also be considered).
- Links to other projects (clustering activities).
- Common visual identity (logo, brochure, poster, and project presentation).
- Video production (project promo videos, videos from the events, training videos).
- E-newsletters (infographics).
- Gadgets for promotion.
- Co-learning sessions, webinars, etc.

2.4 Commitment of project partners

APOLLO partners involved in dissemination will proactively participate in communication and dissemination activities related to the project by exploiting their communication channels to reach the widest audience performed in a structured way, and all these activities will be tracked in this report and its updates. Each dissemination activity will be carried out by the partner who has the most expertise in the specific area or otherwise best fits the action. For the tracking of the actions executed by APOLLO partners, a set of tools for the collection of inputs regarding performed and planned activities has been developed:

- List of Publications Performed and Planned
- List of Events Performed and Planned
- List of Activities Performed and Planned

All partners are required to provide updated information about dissemination events and activities performed and planned by their organization every three months. Partners need to provide to the dissemination leader (FENIX) proofs about events participation (photos, agendas, presentations, videos, etc.) and detailed information about the events (date, place, target audience, size of the audience, type of dissemination such as ppt, brochure, poster, booth, etc.). Project partners are also requested to provide updates about the project's progress and achievements for the APOLLO website and promo materials to be kept up to date.

2.5 Evaluation

Dissemination activities are targeted, and the goal is for them to be successful. To find out if the dissemination strategy was well chosen and well implemented, it is important to build an evaluation component into all major dissemination and communication activities to monitor the quality and to see if they have achieved their aims. Key performance indicators (KPIs) have been defined as the table below shows and monitoring/assessment will be done monthly by the dissemination leader (FENIX).

TABLE 2 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS ACTIVITY

Objective	Tools/channels	KPIs
To create visibility for the project and consortium partners	Visual identity and brand	10,000 hits from at least 10 countries in the first year
	Project website and blog (SEO will be used to maximize impact within search results)	Bounce rate <50%
		At least 25,000 project lifetime views
		At least 48 (1/month) website updates
To raise awareness of project activities and their benefits to all stakeholders	Informative material: printable - (banners, posters, flyers)	5,000 flyers and brochures (print and download) distributed
	Videos – (introductory project video, showcasing project, the challenges it addresses, main objectives, solutions proposed, and the partners involved; and a project progress video)	At least 1,000 views combined across all videos shared.
	Newsletters and use of social media	At least 180 (min. 5/month) posts (across the project duration)
		At least 1,000 followers across all channels by M36
	Participation in industry events	APOLLO representation at min. 5 events (COVID permitting)
Commercial publications in online/offline magazines/ blogs	At least 6 publications	
To disseminate noncommercially sensitive scientific findings that can benefit other R&I activities	Scientific publications in relevant journals	At least 4 scientific journal publications At least 3 industrial journal publications
	Sharing results on online media (research data, photos, reports)	At least 3 results-focused online publications
To demonstrate the technology to relevant industrial stakeholders	Training and workshop sessions	Training materials (e.g. use of DPPs & digital PV marketplace, recycling process operation) and at least 1 training session with min. 50 attendees
		At least 2 workshops with min. 50 attendees
	Project event for customer demonstrations	At least 1 event with min. 150 attendees
To foster relationships and share results with other relevant projects	Engaging with other relevant European, national or regional initiatives, funding programmes and platforms	At least 2 joint events (virtual or physical) with other projects organised and completed;
		APOLLO presence in at least 4 events organised by other projects
To shape and support the Implementation of policy initiatives and decisions	Lobbying at the EC level and through EARTO (European Association of Research and Technology Organisations) for the development of better legislation and initiatives for PV recycling, PV panel recyclability (design for recycling), and PV passports.	Project representation in at least 1 working group.

3. Project identity and public image

Visual and graphic representation allows easier identification of the project for the public as well as a higher chance to increase visibility. The identity of the APOLLO project during the dissemination activities is presented in the following section.

Objectives of the project identity are:

- To develop a design structure that would accommodate standard project identity elements, a variable visual identity in various uses, and be able to convey thematic information when needed.
- To allow immediate recognition of the APOLLO project, thanks to standardized communication templates meant for external audiences.
- To develop specific guidelines and structures related to the project, such as a definite set of colors and/or typography. These guidelines should be applied to templates that are easy to adapt, understand, and use by the project partners.

3.1 Project logo

The initial task for the dissemination of material design is logo development. The logo has been recreated by FENIX in vector format at the beginning of the project to define a distinguishable project identity. The logo was intended to be simple and recognizable. While designing the logo, it was important to keep in mind that it reflects the actual branding trends, so that the design is up to date during the whole project lifecycle. The target audience must identify the logo at first glance; therefore, the logo should be easy to remember and reflect the project's aim. Two versions of the APOLLO logo were created.

FIGURE 2 APOLLO LOGO HORIZONTAL AND VERTICAL

Project logo can be used in the following cases:

- In all documents developed under the framework of the APOLLO project, in documents to be submitted to the EC (e.g., deliverables).
- PowerPoint presentations to be used for communication and dissemination activities to be carried out by each participant under the framework of the project, in all promo materials.
- On the APOLLO website, and the websites of the participants with a link to the project website.

3.2 Brand manual

It is important to follow and respect the project's visual identity to maximize the impact on the audience. For this reason, a brand manual has been created, outlining the visual identity guidelines (color palette, logo variants, typography, and applications). The logos and brand manual can be downloaded from the project website (<https://www.apolloproject.eu/publications>).

FIGURE 3 APOLLO BRAND MANUAL

4. Project website

The APOLLO project website was created and launched during the early stage of the project under the domain www.apolloproject.eu. The web hosting and domain were purchased by FENIX. Google Analytics is used as a tool to monitor Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and was implemented at an early stage of the project (e.g., views, users, countries, languages, browsers, devices, etc.). Another KPI that will be tracked is the number of downloads from the project website (e.g., promo materials, and newsletters). The website was designed to be displayed on various devices such as desktop, mobile, or tablet.

FIGURE 4 WEBSITE ANALYTICS 31/05/2024

The information included on the project website is likely to be valuable even after the project has finished. Therefore, the consortium aims to ensure that the website will continue to exist after the project funding has finished. The project website is considered the central place for all information regarding the project; therefore, it will be updated regularly and will contain all publicly available information.

4.1 Description

The website has been designed by FENIX and the main aim is to address the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have:

- What is the project about?
- Who is participating in the project?
- What additional details are available?
- Who to contact for more information?

The website itself contains the following information:

- general information about the project
- Information about project consortium
- list of news and events
- all public material generated by the project
- links to social network profiles
- newsletter subscription
- contact information

4.1.1 Home and Concept pages

The “Home” page of the APOLLO website contains basic information about the project. The upper part of the screen shows the project’s logo, links for the social profiles, newsletter subscription, and a navigation panel. At the top of the page, there is the project’s title, a short project overview (goal, funding, and consortium), and links to other pages with more information.

The next section is an overview of the latest project’s news and events. In the footer newsletter subscription, funding, social media links, and privacy policy can be found as shown in the Figure below. The “Concept” page presents key information, objectives, and milestones of the APOLLO project. This page will undergo updates as the project progresses.

FIGURE 5 APOLLO HOME PAGE

4.1.2 Consortium and Demonstration pages

The “Consortium” page is at the time of writing this deliverable under construction and will contain information about the APOLLO partners, with actual logos and references to their website. Description of the consortium partners “about” is displayed, while “role in the project” will be added later in the project as well. This part of the website will be static, except for the case of a partner change in the project or a logo change. At the time of writing this deliverable, the “Demonstration” page is under development and will be updated as the project progresses.

4.1.3 News & Events page

The “News & Events” page contains a list of news and events, which will include project progress updates, meetings of the project partners, and important events such as conferences, fairs, and workshops as shown in the Figure below. This page will be regularly updated. Short information about the most recent news is reflected on the “Home” page.

4.1.4 Resources – Publications

The “Resources” page in the navigation menu contains publications (publications, newsletters, and public deliverables) and promotional materials. It will contain all public materials created and published by the project. Subsections and pages can be added based on the project’s requirements and progress at any time.

4.1.5 Resources - Gallery

This page will contain photos and pictures from various events and meetings project partners participate in. Additionally, galleries from project meetings, such as general assembly meetings, also serve as meeting reports, presenting insights into the consortium gatherings.

4.1.6 Contact page

The „Contact page” provides email contact information for the Project Coordinator and the Communication and Dissemination Manager.

4.2 Cookies

Cookies are small text files stored on a user’s computer by their browser. They have many applications, such as: tracking users on a website, remembering user preferences, enabling auto-logins for returning visitors, and enhancing website security. The APOLLO project website has also implemented a cookies policy to help the site provide a better user experience. In general, cookies are used to retain user preferences, store information, and provide tracking data to third-party applications like Google Analytics.

5. Promotional materials

Initial promotional materials (leaflet, roll-up poster, PowerPoint presentation) will be designed to support communication and dissemination activities of the APOLLO project, as part of task 12.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities. The leaflet will be available for the attendees of the dissemination events, the roll-up will serve as the visual representation of the project, and the presentation will support speakers.

6. Videos

One of the essential methods for effective product dissemination is the creation and publication of videos. With in-house video production, FENIX will lead the creation of videos for the APOLLO project. A graphical video illustrating the project objectives, demos, partners, and social impact will be created within the project's first year.

A complex video, including interviews with key partners, filming from demo sites, and voice-over will be produced toward the end of the project. All videos will then be implemented into the APOLLO project website, uploaded on the YouTube channel, shared on social profiles, and thematic portals, among partners, and presented during events. A short-format YouTube video was released in M2 of the project and is available on the project's YouTube channel (www.youtube.com/@apollo-project-eu).

7. E-Newsletter

The newsletter subscription form on the project website was created using the Mailchimp tool and is directly linked to the contact database, where all subscribers are collected for future newsletter campaigns in compliance with GDPR policies. The subscription process is designed as a single opt-in with Captcha to prevent spam and fake accounts.

E-newsletters will be designed by FENIX with the contribution of project partners and released regularly, starting at M6. Each partner will share the e-newsletter among their contacts. The e-newsletter will be directly sent to the APOLLO subscribers who subscribed through the project website and published on social network profiles, the project website, thematic portals, etc. E-newsletter subscription follows the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) regarding the protection of personal data.

8. Social media campaign

During the start of the project, a LinkedIn profile page was created to maximize the visibility of published results and the participation of project partners in international events, as well as to gather feedback from stakeholders. Additionally, a YouTube channel was established as a platform for sharing both long and short-format videos.

The links to these social media platforms have been added to the project website and will be included in all future newsletters. FENIX manages and updates the profiles based on the partners' contributions (general information about the project, updates about the project progress, dissemination activities, infographics, and news from the related field).

As the project progresses, paid ad campaigns will be considered to boost the most important posts to reach the maximum amount of target audiences. Public workshop invitations, crucial project progress reports, and other milestones will be considered for paid ads campaigns.

FIGURE 6 APOLLO LINKEDIN PROFILE

9. Publications

As stated in GA's Specific rules, Article 17, each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. It must:

- a) At the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications.
- b) Ensure open access to the deposited publication - via the repository - under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the license may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g., CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND).
- c) information is given via the repository about any research output, or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must be:

- open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent
- in line with the FAIR principles and provide information at least about the following:
 - publication (author(s))
 - title
 - date of publication
 - publication venue
 - Horizon Europe or Euratom funding
 - grant project name, acronym, and number
 - licensing terms
 - persistent identifiers for the publication
 - authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant
 - where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs

10. List of publications and events

The APOLLO project partners have identified journals and magazines in which they are going to publish the project results. They also have identified conferences, seminars, and fairs in which they are going to participate and publish the project results. The initial list can be found in Table 3.

TABLE 3 DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES IDENTIFIED

Publications and events identified	
Publications	Progress in Photovoltaics, Energies, and Energy Policy, journals including Advances in Materials Research, Metall. Mater. Trans, Separation and Purification Technology and U PVSEC Proceedings, EEI magazine, the Project Repository journal, Energy Manager Magazine, Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells, Advanced Energy Materials, Progress in Photovoltaics, Chemistry Communications, Ultrasonics Sonochemistry, Green Chemistry, Nature Energy
Participation at fairs, seminars, workshops, or conferences	Annual European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference, PVSEC, Silicon PV, Intersolar, EIF, HOPV, MRS, PVSEC, ISOS, European PV Solar Energy Conference, PSCO, MRS, e-MRS, PVSEC, World Sustainable Energy Days, European Sustainable Energy Week, PSCO, Techblick, EU PVSEC, Annual Meeting on Photonic Devices, International Symposia and Innovative Solar Cells, European Green and Sustainable Chemistry Conference, AGChem, IEEE PVSC, WCPEC

10.1 Proof of events

Project partners are required to provide to the dissemination leader (FENIX) proof of dissemination and communication events and activities they participated in (e.g., photos, presentations, videos, website links, press releases, etc.). These proofs will be uploaded as an attachment to an event record in the Microsoft List used for collecting updates and inputs from the partners.

11. Press releases

APOLLO project is going to publish press releases about the project's important milestones and achievements, shared through project partners' channels, the APOLLO website, on the Build Up portal, and via social media profiles.

12. Dissemination activities

There are other dissemination and communication activities either performed or planned that can have a significant impact on the widest possible dissemination of the APOLLO project, e.g. promo materials, print materials, videos, media articles, cluster activity, training activity, newsletter, interview, activity performed by partner, etc. Every three months the list will be reviewed.

13. Clustering activities

Project partners will seek collaboration with other projects that could complement activities and provide synergies enhancing dissemination. Common events will be planned and shared on the APOLLO website to inform about the cluster projects, associations, and cluster activities.

14. Conclusion

In conclusion, this report has outlined the dissemination strategy for the APOLLO project, encompassing the identification of the dissemination channels, target audiences, stakeholders, as well as partners' roles and responsibilities. The document has also delineated the actions already identified and planned for the project.

Dissemination activities will be conducted at national, international, and EU levels by all APOLLO partners throughout the project's duration. These activities will be closely monitored, and the strategy plan will be periodically updated to ensure alignment with project objectives and evolving needs.

By implementing this comprehensive dissemination strategy, we aim to maximize the visibility and impact of the APOLLO project, effectively engage with key stakeholders, and ultimately achieve the project goals. Continuous evaluation and adaptation of the approach will be key to ensuring the success of the dissemination efforts.

